

Through the looking glass of astrophysicist Kozyrev. Can mirrors be transmitters?

One of the first to encounter this effect in a scientific experiment were Florentine academicians of the 17th century. In 1667, in a voluminous collective work - a kind of report on their scientific research - they described a seemingly strange experiment.

A concave mirror was installed at a considerable distance from a two-hundred-kilogram block of ice. At the same time, it was discovered that at its focus the air temperature decreased noticeably. Then Italian scientists concluded that cold, like heat, spreads by radiation.

Today, based on the laws of thermodynamics, we would probably talk about a slightly different mechanism: it is not cold that penetrates into the focus of the mirror, but heat, as it were, “pulled out” from it and rushes outward. In other words, a concave mirror has the properties of not only a receiving antenna, but also a transmitting antenna.

This effect is well known in radio engineering: just look at parabolic radar or satellite television antennas. Apparently, the so-called “Kozyrev mirrors” - a special system of concave aluminum mirrors - also have similar properties.

According to the hypothesis proposed by Professor N.A. Kozyrev, these mirrors can focus various types of radiation, including from biological objects. The predictions of the brilliant scientist were confirmed by experiments on distant interactions: clairvoyance, telepathy, etc.

Such work, in particular, is carried out by Novosibirsk scientists under the leadership of Academician of the Russian Academy of Medical Sciences V.P. Treasurer. Researchers are getting truly amazing results. Thus, in the early 90s of the 20th century, for the first time in the history of science, two global experiments on the telepathic transmission of visual images were carried out.

The purpose of these experiments was “to study the information field of the Earth (“living space”) in the process of distant communications between people” who are thousands of kilometers apart from each other and do not use traditional technical means of communication.

At the same time, the experimenters set themselves another task: to find out how the quality of telepathic communication was affected by “Kozyrev’s mirrors,” in the internal space of which people were placed transmitting and receiving telepathic information. These multi-day experiments involved more than four and a half thousand participants from twelve countries.

In December 1991, during the Arctic Circle experiment, mental transmission of images was carried out from the polar village of Dikson, and reception was carried out at various points in the newly collapsed Soviet Union. And a year and a half later, in June 1993, the images were broadcast from Novosibirsk and Dikson, and received in various geographical locations in Europe, Asia and America.

Performed at a very high scientific level, these experiments convincingly proved not only the possibility of distant transmission and reception of mental images, but also the special stability of reception if the subjects were in the focus of concave “Kozyrev mirrors”. The possibility of “programmed input” (using special technologies) of figurative information into the Earth’s

information field with the condition of its reception (reproduction) on a specific date and time was also confirmed.

Here is what their leader, Vlail Petrovich Kaznacheev, says about one of these experiments: "An advance, unannounced in the program, image transfer session took place on December 18, 1991.

Its participant K. Dolgopyatov, born during the full moon, being in the space of "mirrors" in a special state of consciousness, "mounted" a package of figurative information into a laser beam oriented towards the full moon, with the installation of receiving this information by other participants in the experiment on December 20 and 22 .

It was found that elements of this program were consistently accepted at the appointed time and continued to be accepted during subsequent sessions. Analysis of the numerical parameters of the sessions... confirms the reality of the perception simultaneously in many points of Eurasia of information previously entered into the earth's information space.

Repeating the experiment with another participant who was born out of connection with the full moon, without "Kozyrev's mirrors", without a laser or without its orientation towards the Moon was not successful... We are closer to proving the interconnections of intellectual fields and recognizing the capabilities of the human mind to receive information regardless of geography and time."

At the same time, it was convincingly shown that the quality of telepathic contact largely depends on the training of people in this non-traditional field. In other words, it was firmly established that in all these cases it is not just a person and not just a mirror that is working, but a complex "man-mirror" and that each of the components of this complex has independent value.

On the one hand, it is very important for a person to be able to tune in, concentrate, and put his consciousness into a special state. On the other hand, its "technical equipment" is important. It turns out that the system of "Kozyrev's mirrors" can turn an ordinary person into almost a magician...

"Neither wash off nor scrape off..."

This was clearly demonstrated, for example, by an experiment by a student of academician A.P. Okladnikov (1908-1981), artist and scientist Mikhail Ugrin. This is what he said about one of his attempts to convey mental images using "Kozyrev's mirrors" located in the Novosibirsk Academgorodok: "Following the advice of the academician (V.P. Kaznacheev. - V.P.), I tried to convey... my own image to her niece, who at that time was seven thousand kilometers away, in Pushchinskiye Klyuchi, where she was treating her tonsils in a healing bath.

And it turned out that thermophilic bacteria, having somehow perceived this thought form, "laid out" a very clear portrait of me on the walls of the bathtub, which was recorded on photographic film by several observers.

As for the "portrait" - it is still on the inner wall of this bath." Protocol recording of the experiment: October 5, 1996, Yaselchuk Natalya Viktorovna, St. Petersburg: "Last year on Intercession I was in Pushchinskie Klyuchi with my nephew Slava and Aunt O. M. Ugrina. We

swam in the bathtub, looked at the bizarre patterns that had formed on the walls of the bathhouse. There were so many curls, zigzags, and ornaments there!

Centimeter by centimeter we looked at the extraordinary drawings created by nature. Suddenly, unexpectedly, we saw a clear portrait (profile) of Mikhail Ugrin. The deposits of salts or algae (it is difficult for me to determine the nature of this material) exactly repeated the contours of the face, hair, and beard. M. Ugrin has an extraordinary appearance, and nature easily made a photograph from its own natural material!"

You can, of course, talk about coincidence: if you have imagination, you can see a lot of things in the chaos of lines. However, there is no need to rush: it turns out that similar phenomena, but associated with deceased people - who have already gone into a "parallel" world to us - have been known for a long time.

Thus, "after the death of the rector of the cathedral in Landaf Vaughan, a damp spot suddenly appeared on the wall of the cathedral - a colony of fungi took exactly the outline of the face of the deceased" (1902. February 8).

A similar incident occurred in mid-1923 in Oxford. A miraculous portrait suddenly appeared on the wall of Christ Church, surprisingly reminiscent of the appearance of the former rector of this cathedral, Liddell, who died in 1898. "You don't have to stretch your imagination to recognize a person's head. It is immediately visible on the wall, as if drawn by the confident hand of a master. It is not an engraving, nor a drawing, nor a sculpture, but it cannot be overlooked" (T.P. and Cassell weekly, 1926. September 11).

No less mysterious was the appearance of miraculous faces in 1971 in the small Spanish town of Belmez de la Moraleda near Cordoba. For the first time, a resident of the town, Maria Gomez Comara, discovered a strange portrait one morning on the tiled floor of her kitchen.

The image could neither be washed off nor scraped off. The son replaced the tiles, but the faces continued to appear. And more and more new. In one of the mysterious portraits, the old-timers of Belmez recognized a long-dead fellow countryman. It turned out that he was buried exactly in the place where Mary's house now stood - there once was a cemetery.

Mysterious faces appeared for several months. Experienced experts, photo reporters, and television crews were invited, but the version of fraud was not confirmed. There was only one thing left to do - seal the room and after a while see if anything new would appear on the floor. Which is what was done.

Here is what the famous lawyer Antonio Palacios Luque says about this: "I reliably and firmly sealed the kitchen of Dona Maria Gomez and at the same time recorded these actions with the help of the notary Julian Echeverría and scientists.

Three months later, the seal was removed, and I swear to you, I saw that the figures had changed during this time... I do not know of a painting technique that could be used to apply these images. Staying in a closed kitchen, the faces changed! During these three months, in my opinion, no one could penetrate there until I personally removed the seal... I can say with all confidence that this was not a hoax. This is a paranormal phenomenon, and I have no doubt about it."

What struck the lawyer most was that during the three months that the kitchen was locked and sealed, some of the images changed their perspective. And one profile actually turned in the opposite direction! At the sight of this miracle, the notary recalls, he was seized with real horror...

Science has not yet been able to explain this mysterious phenomenon. Meanwhile, reports about the appearance of mysterious miraculous images that cannot be washed off even with acids have continued to come from different parts of the planet for centuries. Images of people, skulls, eagles, crosses, banners, multi-colored stripes, religious and political symbols appear on walls, floors, and window glass...

Attempts to explain these images by the property of people to see imaginary pictures in random combinations of spots and lines most often do not stand up to serious criticism. It remains to be assumed that these images come from the subtle world.

Including from the world where the information structure of a person ("soul") "goes" after the death of his physical body. Of course, there are still a lot of questions here. Who is behind these messages? If this is a kind of reminder of the dead about themselves, then why is it, for what purpose? Why do these particular images appear and not other images? What is the mechanism of their occurrence? It is unlikely that anyone will undertake to answer these questions unambiguously.

The experiment with "Kozyrev's mirrors", in which M. Ugrin participated, so far indicates only one possible nature of the "pictures": most likely, this is the materialization of thought forms emitted by someone....

Materialization? Nothing supernatural...

First, let's think about: what, in fact, is the difference between all the objects that we see around us? It would seem that it's a "no brainer" - shape, size, material, color... Everything is correct. But if we look a little deeper, we will understand something very important: they differ only in the "information task"!

Judge for yourself. All these objects consist of the same elementary particles: electrons, protons, neutrons... If these particles come together in one combination, you get an atom of invisible and light oxygen; if they come together in another, you get an atom of heavy and opaque lead. Continuous combinatorics: the way atoms of different chemical elements combine determines what material will emerge, with what chemical properties, weight, color, smell...

And then - it's even more familiar: make whatever your heart desires from these materials. So it turns out that everything that we see is ultimately "made" (and in fact, "materialized") from the same first bricks - like from the parts of a children's construction set - only according to different "drawings".

Let's not go deep into who comes up with these "blueprints", but let's imagine a hypothetical: there is someone who can easily "disassemble" one structure (for example, oxygen molecules) and assemble another from the resulting "parts" (elementary particles) - for example, gold ring with diamonds. Then people around will start gasping: "Miracle!"

But to figure it out, there is nothing supernatural in this: science has simply not yet put this “technology” on stream. But it is moving towards this by leaps and bounds. It has already learned (albeit in scanty quantities) to produce new chemical elements using nuclear accelerators, but in fact, just new combinations of “first bricks”. What happens next is a matter of technology and financial investments...

No, there is nothing “miraculous” about materialization! A miracle is something that most people do not yet know how to do. Two hundred years ago, television would have been a miracle. And in the Middle Ages, any modern technical craft could have landed you at the stake - “magic and witchcraft!”

The achievements of modern science are, of course, impressive. But for a long time I have not left the feeling that most of her decisions, to put it mildly, are not the most effective.

That she uses brute force - a sledgehammer and an autogen - to break open the doors of armored safes. But any safe can open on its own: even a child can open it - if, of course, they correctly enter the required combination of numbers on the combination lock. Maybe it is in this direction that science will develop in the future - to look for “keys” and “codes”, and not to increase the weight of the “sledgehammer” - its energy power?

However, she will first need to significantly correct her ingrained views on the universe. And it seems that this process has already begun. Today, science is getting closer and closer to that fragile line that separates consciousness and matter. And he begins to understand that under certain conditions (with knowledge of the “code”) a thought can materialize.

As the famous psychologist and philosopher G. Price said back in 1949, “every idea has an inherent tendency to be realized in some physical form, to turn into a certain object or “materialize”...

It is quite possible that an idea is capable of transforming already existing material formations in a certain way.” And this is not an allegory. And the “hypothetical” story we cited with the materialization of a ring “out of nothing” is not fiction.

Such miracles, for example, were demonstrated in abundance in India by a unique personality - Sathya Sai Baba. As thousands of eyewitnesses testify, he literally materialized gifts out of thin air for his visitors: rosary beads, rings, gold pendants... From his open palm, the healing powder “vibhuti”, appearing literally out of nowhere, can endlessly rain down. All this was repeatedly filmed on photo and film, and the videos went around the whole world. The reliability of the phenomenon is not disputed even by the most inveterate skeptics...

However, let us return to M. Ugrin’s experiment with “Kozyrev mirrors”. It can be assumed that the materialization of the thought images emitted by him took place on the wall of the bathtub. Through the “funnel” - the focus of a concave mirror, and then - through another dimension - these thought forms reached the addressee and launched the program of their materialization.

However, a natural question may arise here: why did the image sent by Ugrin “imprint” not as a telepathic image in the niece’s head, but on the wall of the pool? The answer to this question almost half a century before this experiment was given by the same G. Price: “Every idea strives to enter consciousness, if possible.

And if telepathy is a genuine fact (I am sure that it is), then every idea tends to enter any consciousness, it does not matter whose. But every time she tries to do this, she comes across the threshold of consciousness and only in rare cases does she manage to cross it...

If an idea cannot enter the consciousness directly, it can still do so indirectly, through the sense organs. The threshold of consciousness is more passable for sensory perceptions than for thoughts and images... It follows from this that an idea embodies itself in matter in order to thus enter someone's consciousness."

It seems that this is exactly what happened in the case of Ugrin. Unable to break into the consciousness of his niece, the thought image emitted by him in the focus of "Kozyrev's mirrors" materialized in a suitable physical environment, forcing deposits (salts, mold?) on the wall of the bathhouse to take the desired shape.

Such "information tasks" (ideas) can be so strong that they will manifest themselves (materialize) again and again - even if the tiles are completely replaced, as was the case in Spain.

Reaction of the information field?

However, let's return to the concave "Kozyrev mirrors". Researchers working with them have identified other interesting patterns. Thus, unexpectedly for the participants in the experiments, it turned out that a person placed at the focus of these mirrors, and in fact - at the focus of his own reflected radiation, suddenly has strange visions.

Some of them relate to the past, some to the spatially distant present. In fact, this became scientific confirmation of a phenomenon already familiar to us from numerous "unscientific" evidence. During experiments with "Kozyrev mirrors", absolutely amazing effects were discovered. For example, plasmoids often appear at the focus of these mirrors - luminous objects like UFOs or ball lightning...

Not only that, Academician Kaznacheev also spoke about other strange phenomena: "The symbol of N.K. Roerich's "Banner of Peace", prepared for figurative translation, was brought into the space of the experimental installation of "Kozyrev's mirrors" on December 24, 1990 by tester M. Vertipolokh.

At this moment, a "force field" arose around the installation; a little later, a flash of "plasmoid" and magnetic and dowsing anomalies were recorded inside it; the smell of ozone was felt in the room, and a moving luminous disk-shaped object was observed above the building where the experiment was carried out.

At the same time, geophysical services on Dikson recorded a particularly strong disturbance of the magnet and ionosphere, and bright, colored northern lights were observed over the village. In five of the seven experiments of this period, a "reaction" of the information field was noted in the form of a luminous object with a trail that appeared and disappeared in the polar sky with an accuracy of up to a minute at the moments of the beginning and end of experimental work in "Kozyrev's mirrors."

Academician Kaznacheev believes that these phenomena are the reaction of the Earth's information field to the "introduction" of human thought forms into it with the help of

“Kozyrev’s mirrors.” It is possible that this is so. And the question immediately arises: what power does information have if it is capable of causing such physical phenomena?

And the next one: what capabilities do concave mirrors have, if the thought (information) of an ordinary person (for example, M. Ugrin) - far from a magician - is capable of materializing in physical form at a distance of thousands of kilometers? And one more thing: what happens at the focus of concave mirrors, if the planet (and perhaps another mind) begins to respond to the thought of a person placed in such a focus?

The properties of magic tricks have not yet been fully studied, but it can already be assumed that great discoveries await scientists here. Thus, there is information about experiments with two concave mirrors placed opposite each other with specially treated reflective surfaces.

If the focal points of these mirrors are aligned with great precision, then under certain conditions small objects placed at this point suddenly hover in the air, as if they were not affected by the force of gravity. It seems that a special spatial effect occurs at the focal point of the concave mirror.

Another, no less intriguing, phenomenon is associated with time anomalies. Thus, in some experiments with “Kozyrev’s mirrors,” telepathic information was received by the recipient several hours earlier (!) than it was emitted by the inductor. Can modern science explain these space-time anomalies at the focus of concave mirrors?

Is it possible to focus time?

According to the original hypothesis of Professor N.A. Kozyrev, time is one of the main forms of energy in the Cosmos, an active factor, moreover, the main organizing force of all processes in the Universe.

It is the energy of time that is the “fuel” for our Sun and other stars. It spreads throughout the Universe instantly and has not only directionality (sign), but also density, with which the passage of time is directly related.

“All processes where there are cause-and-effect transitions,” Kozyrev believed, “emit or absorb time. Where there are no these transitions, time simply does not exist. Let’s say it does not exist in “black holes,” because nothing happens there: the gigantic attraction of this mass, collapsing into itself, stopped all movement.

Even the movement of molecules and atoms. And time also stopped. But the stars, on the contrary, are a boiling cauldron... And from there comes a huge release of time. Moreover, it flows either faster or slower, depending on the conditions.”

To confirm his views, Kozyrev created original instruments that made it possible to literally “weigh” the flow of time. Using these devices, the scientist convincingly proved that time density is greater where non-stationary processes occur.

And it doesn’t matter what kind: be it the mixing of hot and cold water in a vessel, the dissolution of sugar in a glass of boiling water, or the seething of gigantic masses of stellar matter. It turned out that with increasing entropy (chaos), the density of time increases.

In other words, when “order” decreases, it gives up its energy to time. This discovery alone is enough to recognize Kozyrev as an outstanding scientist and thinker on a global scale. However, the searching mind of the astronomy professor did not stop there.

A seditious idea was born: the density of time can be weakened with the help of special screens or strengthened by “focusing” time with the help of concave mirrors. ON THE. Kozyrev did not have time to implement his ideas, but, as we see, they turned out to be prophetic. "Kozyrev's Mirrors" proved that he was on the right track and that concave mirrors really have amazing properties.

Apparently, N.A. Kozyrev was one of the first on Earth to understand that the Second Law of Thermodynamics is not a universal law of Nature, since it is not satisfied on the scale of the entire universe: this law is valid locally, but not globally.

A blatant contradiction for the Second Law of Thermodynamics is the emergence of new, previously non-existent stars, for this fact clearly demonstrates a process with negative entropy. If stars were born and born rarely, one by one, then this process could be explained based on probabilistic concepts of the evolution of matter in galaxies.

It is quite possible that due to inevitable fluctuations in the density of interstellar gas in galaxies, with a certain probability, conditions are created where the local gravitational potential becomes greater than a certain critical value and in this place the density and mass of the incoming gas increases, which will ultimately end in millions of years the birth of an infant star. This process is quite possible, it is well understood and described in the scientific literature.

The consequence of this process is the depletion of the surrounding space in interstellar gas, which reduces the likelihood of the birth of other stars here. To explain the observed group birth of stars, scientists had to assume that giant gas and dust clouds with masses of hundreds and thousands of solar masses arise in the Galaxy.

During the process of gravitational collapse, such a massive cloud is divided into fragments, each of which serves as the embryo of a future star. Astronomers know the places of collective appearance of nascent stars in the constellations Taurus, Unicorn, Cygnus and others. It would seem that everything is correct?

But! If a hypothetical massive cloud of gas and dust existed from the moment of the “creation of the world,” then why only in our era, that is, after billions of years of vegetation, did it begin to shrink, marking the beginning of the group birth of stars? Or maybe it was previously not subject to the universal law of gravity?

But if it did not exist before as a massive cloud of gas and dust, then it was formed in the process of evolution. And this is a process with negative entropy.

Even more surprising is that in other galaxies, individual regions of millions of cubic parsecs are observed, covered by the total process of star birth! These are genuine stellar “maternity hospitals”, where the number of “babies” is measured in many thousands.

And it is not at all clear what causes the birth of young galaxies whose age does not exceed 1 billion years

N.A. Kozyrev could have thought this way or something like this, realizing that the visible Universe, as an evolving object, is not self-sufficient, based on the qualities that modern science endows it with.

We need some additional factor that could constantly fuel the engine of evolution, maintaining an unbroken endless chain of its constituent elements: birth - death - birth, etc.

Three pillars of Kozyrev's concept

This reason, according to N.A. Kozyrev, is the current time.

1. Time is not just a measure for determining the duration of any processes. Time, according to Kozyrev, is an extraphysical substance that interacts with all objects and participates in all processes, filling them with energy (the type or nature of energy is not specified). In other words, time itself carries energy. And if so, it is characterized by a parameter that N. A. Kozyrev called "time flow density."

The flow of time, interacting with systems, increases their internal energy. Since all objects of the physical world exist in time, they are fueled by the flow of time and for this reason always have a positive energy balance.

2. From here follows the most important conclusion, which can rather be called philosophical than physical: there are no dead objects in the Universe, everything that exists in it carries certain signs of life (of course, we are not talking about biological life). It is well known that galaxies, stars, and large planets evolve. But the satellites of the planets, which seem to be frozen in eternity, do they fit the definition of "living"?

Kozyrev answered: "Yes!" If this is so, then the concept of energy replenishment over time can find direct confirmation.

3. The third most important principle of Kozyrev's concept sounds unusual and unusual: The entire Universe, from the point of view of time, is a point. Kozyrev, proceeding, naturally, not from experimental, but only from intuitive ideas about the nature of time, believed that time appears immediately and simultaneously (forgive the tautology), i.e., with one phase in the entire Universe.

Therefore, the entire universe is covered by a coherent time flow, just like the beads of a necklace are covered by a single thread. "Time does not spread in the Universe, it appears everywhere at once. The entire Universe is projected onto the time axis by one point," the scientist wrote.

That is why, from the standpoint of the special properties of time, galaxies and their clusters have neither length, nor height, nor width, i.e., they have the property of a mathematical point. The most important consequence of this postulate is the fundamental possibility of interactions carried out at an infinitely high speed.

Observational supports for three conceptual pillars

To what extent were the original thoughts of N. A. Kozyrev reflected or confirmed in human practice? Should they be considered as purely abstract ideas about the nature of time, or are they at least indirectly confirmed by observations?

A. The principle of the inapplicability of the Second Law of Thermodynamics to the entire Universe as a whole cannot have direct observational evidence. And this is understandable. After all, to affirm or deny it, we would have to explore the entire universe. But there is indirect evidence that Kozyrev is right - these are young sprouts of new life, both within the Galaxy and among many other galaxies.

Science still does not know where the cause of these origins lies. The energy engine of the Universe remains unknown to science.

b. The second postulate of Kozyrev's concept concerns the density of the flow of time - the universal energy-generating substance, which ultimately provides energy to all things.

Any cosmic object is in the flow of time and therefore its internal energy can never fall to zero: it is always positive. From here followed not a physical, but a deep ideological conclusion: there are no dead objects in the Universe.

In the middle of the twentieth century, when many physicists still took the hypothesis of the "thermal death" of the Universe quite seriously, this conclusion seemed strange to most. Astronomers, for example, considered Mercury a dead planet. And after the failure of attempts to find water-filled canals and blue-violet vegetation along their banks on Mars, Mars seemed just as lifeless.

In their opinion, there was nothing to say about the satellites of the planets: all of them, including the Moon, were a priori considered dead due to the exceptional smallness of their masses.

And suddenly in 1956 it turns out that the Moon is showing signs of volcanic activity, since an ejection of lunar material was observed over the Alphonse crater. The luminescent gas left a bright emission line on the spectrograms obtained on November 3, 1956.

It is not surprising that these observations were carried out by Kozyrev. The astronomical world did not believe the Soviet scientist and Western colleagues (in particular, D. Kuiper) accused N. A. Kozyrev of falsifying observations. It took a special examination by specialists from the International Astronomical Union (IAU), which finally officially confirmed the authenticity of the spectrograms and approved the discovery of Kozyrev, who "revitalized" the Moon.

The reliability of these results was confirmed by analysis of lunar soil samples delivered to Earth in 1969 by the American Apollo 11 spacecraft. It was confirmed that many rock samples are of volcanic origin. This means there were volcanoes on the Moon! And after 10 years, the Voyagers spacecraft from the flight path discover eight active volcanoes on Jupiter's moon Io.

But by this time N.A. Kozyrev had already been awarded the diamond medal of the International Academy of Astronautics for the discovery of volcanism on our satellite. Previously Yuri Gagarin brought the same medal to the USSR. Thus, the tectonic activity of small bodies of the solar system confirmed Kozyrev's concept.

V. If N.A. Kozyrev is right and the Universe from the standpoint of his concept can be considered as a point, then it becomes possible to transmit interaction at an infinitely high speed. The general theory of relativity (GTR) denies this possibility. Kozyrev was apparently the first to question the validity of general relativity on an experimental basis.

He conducted experiments that are now world famous, the essence of which is as follows. The scientist placed one of the four resistances in Winston's balanced bridge at the focus of the telescope, and directed the axis of the telescope towards bright celestial objects.

The surprising result of the experiment was not even that the active resistor "felt" the signal from the star, but that sometimes the maximum change in resistance was recorded when the axis of the telescope was shifted relative to the position of the star by several arc seconds.

Taking into account the star's own motion, Kozyrev determined that the maximum signal comes from that point in the celestial sphere where the star will arrive in several tens or hundreds of years, that is, when its light reaches the Earth. The scientist concluded that his instrument registers the star in its real, and not in its apparent, location. Consequently, argued N.A. Kozyrev, it is possible for a signal to propagate at a speed much greater than the speed of light.

But modern positivist (academic) science cannot agree with this. Despite the fact that similar experiments with similar conclusions were carried out by scientists from Novosibirsk, Kozyrev's concept was generally ridiculed by representatives of official science, and Nikolai Alexandrovich's work did not receive any support.

In this regard, one historical parallel is worthy of mention. In 1938, Japanese professor M. Takata, using the results of many years of experiments, showed that the rate of sedimentation of the blood protein albumin changes abruptly 6–8 minutes before the moment when the Sun crosses the mathematical horizon at the observation site.

At the same time, solar radiation did not fall on the test tube with the test drug, as a result of which Takata came to the conclusion about the existence of a new, unknown to science, component of solar radiation. The fact is surprising in itself, but it becomes especially poignant when you consider that 8 minutes is the luminous distance from the Sun to the Earth.

This means that the test tube protein reacts not to a visible star, but to the real Sun, and, thus, indicates the speed of propagation of interaction, much higher than the speed of light. Unfortunately, the outstanding work of the Japanese professor was published in a little-known Austrian meteorological journal and was not further developed.

Thus, it becomes clear that Kozyrev's ideas could not be called groundless or false. Moreover, they were not just logically justified, but stemmed from and were confirmed by non-standard experiments, the results of which most scientists were not ready to explain either then or now.

Those who recognize the greatness of Kozyrev understand that his ideas turned out to be unclaimed by science not because they were devoid of anything significant or were simply false, but solely because they shone in the distance far ahead of the so-called advanced front of science.

Kozyrev, as a heuristic scientist, was far ahead of the scientific thought of the twentieth century, just like A. Chizhevsky, V. Vernadsky, and even earlier - G. Bruno.

In this regard, a legitimate question arises: why does Her Majesty Nature generate talents whose creativity is not needed by contemporaries? Was the appearance of N.A. Kozyrev by chance? Maybe our world didn't need him?

Die in space, live in time

This is what Andrei Voznesensky said about Kozyrev. Is this a poetic invention or a visionary understanding of the mission that fate entrusted to Kozyrev? He came to this world in a harsh and unfair time and his life's path was paved with the most difficult trials. N.A. Kozyrev not only overcame them.

In the fire of his hardships, he strengthened his courage and acquired the strength to challenge the scientific world, which has long been saddled with the concept of one-dimensional, unidirectional and linear time, from the only real point of which, called "the present," scientists cannot move either forward or backward.

Kozyrev argued that through the flow of time one can come into contact with the past and the future. In this regard, N.A. Kozyrev stands on a par with those Great Ones who foresaw the future: Pythagoras, Roger Bacon, Helena Blavatsky, Edgar Cayce and Petrichsky Vanga and many like them.

Apparently, Kozyrev's task was to prepare the consciousness of modern scientists to recognize such an understanding. For this, fate made Kozyrev a scientist, for this he was destined to defend his doctoral dissertation.

And here Providence guided him, because defending his dissertation on the topic of the absence of thermonuclear reactions inside the Sun was possible only by a MIRACLE. And this miracle happened.

The time has come to provide a new understanding of the world, broader than that covered by the modern scientific paradigm. However, it is apparently impossible to expand and, even more so, replace the existing paradigm, ossified in its material-three-dimensional sarcophagus, using only internal forces. We need an external impulse.

In this case, outside help becomes necessary and celestial seers appear on Earth, who draw not fantastic, but real horizons of the future for enchanted people. One of them was N. A. Kozyrev.

He planted the seed of a new concept into public thought, in which His Majesty of Time is assigned the role of a continuous cosmic source, feeding with its energy the movement of all worlds and universes.

Instead of an epilogue

In a short memorial article it is hardly possible to paint a complete portrait of Kozyrev the researcher. I can only sketch a sketch of a pioneer who introduced a completely new layer of concepts into the collective scientific consciousness. Not all researchers share Kozyrev's views; his idea of the world was too original.

The future will show where this extraordinary scientist was right and where he was wrong. But his name is not forgotten, and moreover, over time, it is mentioned on the pages of various publications. Kozyrev had no students, but now many followers have appeared. Schopenhauer said that “at the heights of thought loneliness always reigns.”

N. A. Kozyrev built a nest of his scientific isolation at such a height that many other talents found it impossible to rise to. Paradoxical as it may seem, Kozyrev’s strength lay precisely in his loneliness. If it were not so, then his talent, being dispersed among numerous surroundings, would certainly lose its heuristic power.

He alone managed to convey to future humanity a rock painting of time. Our descendants, like today's archaeologists, will try to recognize not only the meaning of physical time, but also the image of its discoverer, from the meager strokes left behind.

P.S.

The elements of Euclid's geometry are a point (zero-dimensional space) - an object without length, width and height.

If we put a dot on a sheet of paper, then at least we see it, it has at least a small, but size, conditional circle, geometry, when you press a pen or pencil on a sheet of paper on one side (not visible to us), there will be a bulge, on the other, given to us - concavity, color, depending on the color of the paste or pencil, perhaps one click affects the geometry of the entire sheet or a nearby area of the sheet around the point at least.

In space, everything is more complicated ...

What is a point?

What size is it by itself?

Is it stationary in time or does it change there?

If yes, in which direction?

The point can be a portal (entered - exited)?

Is the dot dark energy?

Is the dot dark matter?

Is the dot dark energy and matter at the same time?

Dot is a channel?

Can the hotspot receive a signal?

If yes, at what frequency?

A point is a fractal, but we still don't understand it?

